

Impact of Rural Service Centres on Changing Patterns of Crop Cultivation: A Micro Level Study of Chhotakimath Centre of Jehanabad District, Bihar (2001-2021)

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Abstract

The rural centre provides different types of services to their population as well as the population of their surrounding areas. The Centres serve the important functions of agricultural activities, and plays vital role in the selection of crops by the farmers of area. With the development of service centres the area under vegetable crops cultivation have been increasing. The economy of Bihar State is mainly agriculture based (Census 2011) and approximately 88.70 percent people of Bihar live in rural areas. The main objective of this research paper is to study the impact of rural service centres in the selection of crops by the farmers of the study areas. The study is mainly based on primary data which have been collected through field work and observation by the researcher. The selected micro level study area of Jehanabad district of Bihar is Chhotakimath rural service centre, situated on the eastern bank of Kararua river (Branch of Falgu river). As per observation, it is found that there are changes occurred in crops cultivation in the area concerned and the surrounding areas as a result of increasing facilities in the Chhotakimath rural service centre in the area.

Keywords Rural Service Centre, Crop Diversification, Vegetable Crops, Rural Development.

Introduction

Rural Service Centre provides different types of services to their population as well as the population of the surrounding areas. Rural service centres of many developing countries serve the important functions for providing most of commercial public services for the dispersed rural population. Hence they play vital role in the development of Bihar, because approximately 88.70% people of Bihar live in rural areas. We know that, agriculture is the means of livelihood of major portion of the people of Bihar. It is an important economic activity of rural areas playing an important role in socio-economic and cultural upliftment. But, in the modern days the maximum people of rural areas are unable to get maximum profit from their economic activities due to various causes such as- lack of nearest market centre, transport facilities, educational institutions, medical facilities etc. and unawareness from governmental policies. Due to availability of nearest market facilities, the farmers try to cultivate that type of crops from which they can get maximum profit and for maximum profit, the farming shifted from grain crops cultivation to vegetable crops cultivation. Presently the major rural service centres of Jehanabad district are Kako, Tehata, Okari, Modanganj, Hulasganj, Qazisarai etc of which Chhotakimath is also important for providing services.

Aim of study

The main objective of the present study are-

1. To study the functions of Chhotakimath rural service centre.
2. To study the impact of rural service centres in the selection of crops.

Review of Literature

Many scholars have studied the role of rural service centres, many and contributed extensively and suggested much solution & planning for the rural development to the government. In this context Chang, B.L.(1979); Bromley, R.(1984); Christaller, W.(1933); Katiman, Rostam (1991) have important contribution. B.L. Chang have studied about the role of a small town in Rural-Urban Development in Northern Malaysia, Bromley has

studied about the market centres and its impact on an agricultural development, Katiman Rostam have studied about the role of rural service centres in rural development in Malaysia. In India, Swaminathan (1928); Sinha, M.M.P.(1942); Sinha, V.N.P.(1976); Mandal, R.B.(1981); Sudhir Wanmali & Yassir Islam (1995); Jha, V.N.(2006) and many other scholars have also contributed important role in this field. At present, Kumar, Anil (2007); Kumar, Vishwavijay (2010) and Kumar, Vivek (2019) of Patna University, like young scholars have also contributed in this regard. Which have spelt out the role of Rural Service Centres in agricultural development of their surrounding service areas.

Hypothesis The following hypotheses have been formulated-

1. Facilities in rural service centres increase with the passage of time.
2. Pattern of crops cultivation change with the development of rural service centre.

Methodology

The present study is mainly based on primary as well as secondary sources of data. The primary data have been collected from field survey by interviewing the villagers and the secondary data have been obtained from census Report, 2011, books, research journals and unpublished PhD theses as well as internet. The data have been analysed by suitable statistical methods and represented through tables, maps & diagrams.

Analysis

Study area: The selected micro level study area of Bihar is Chhotakimath Rural Service Centre of Jehanabad district, situated on the eastern bank of Kararua river (Branch of Falgu river) in Modanganj Block. It has geographical coordinates 25° 18' 43" N and 85° 08' 07" E. As per census 2011, total population of Chhotakimath Rural Service Centre is 1363 (Note- The settlement area of Chhotakimath Rural Service Centre is a combined settlement area of Chhotakimath village (Population 1073 people) and adjacent settlement area of a tola of Bahrapur village of Patna district having population 290). IZ is situated approximately 35 KMs. South from Patna Zero mile and approximately 20 Km. North-east from Jehanabad railway station. It is demarcated by Bahrapur village in north, Dewra in south, Shadipur in east and Sultanpur in the west. The villages who get different types of services from Chhotakimath rural service centre are mainly Chhotakimath, Bahrapur, Bahrapur (Bigha), Olipur, Kisunganj, Shadipur, Dewra, Planipar, Sultanpur and Marhipar.

